

M3.12 Onboarding Standard Operation Procedure (SOP)

Tier: Technology

Executive Summary

This milestone delivers a draft Standard Operating Procedure (SOP) to support the onboarding of new Training Coordinators (TrCs) within the ELIXIR Training Coordinators Group (TrCG). The purpose of this document is to ensure consistency and quality in the onboarding process, promoting early alignment with ELIXIR's strategic goals and operational standards. The SOP is targeted for TrCs and Deputy/Interim TrCs officially assigned by ELIXIR Nodes. The SOP helps guide entry into the coordinator role. This milestone considers past/existing onboarding practices, WP3 milestones and deliverables, and feedback from existing TrCs from different Nodes and the ELIXIR TrCG. The document will undergo review and further refinement to become a deliverable, which will be a reference tool for future onboarding of TrCs.

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

TrC(s)	Training Coordinator(s)
TrCG	Training Coordinator Group
TrP	Training Platform
SOP	Standard Operating Procedure

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Purpose and Scope

Standard Operating Procedure (SOP) defines a structured onboarding process for new and upcoming ELIXIR Training Coordinators (TrCs) at both Node and Platform levels. The purpose of this SOP is to support TrCs in understanding their role, responsibilities, and expectations, enabling them to efficiently onboard and actively engage with ELIXIR Training Platform (TrP) activities and the wider ELIXIR network. The SOP provides practical guidance on getting started in the role, alongside links to key resources and references, ensuring efficient and consistent integration of TrCs across ELIXIR Nodes. This SOP is connected to and complements ELIXIR-STEERS WP4.

Each ELIXIR Node is required to appoint a TrC to help coordinate training activities within their Node, which may include the development of national training platforms, collaboration with and support of instructors, and contributions to training resources, tools, practices, and services. While the TrC role is defined, differences in Node structures and operational practices necessitate a standardised onboarding framework. Beyond Node-level responsibilities, TrCs are members of the ELIXIR community and contribute to the Coordinators' Triangle, Training Coordinator Group (TrCG), and potentially the ELIXIR TrP.

ELIXIR's training strategy is defined and implemented through the TrP. TrCs are expected to align Node-level training activities with this strategy, fostering a sustainable training environment that supports professional development, infrastructure access, contribution, and recognition within ELIXIR.

Onboarding a TrC role

In order to support new TrCs in contributing to ELIXIR TrCG, Node/ELIXIR training strategy and the ELIXIR TrP, an onboarding process is defined to ensure a smooth and informed integration. As

members of the TrCG and ELIXIR stakeholder community¹, TrCs are added to relevant mailing lists, receive the ELIXIR weekly brief and follow relevant news via ELIXIR webpages.

TrCs are encouraged to engage with the ELIXIR TrP, which coordinates the ELIXIR Training Strategy and provides a dedicated onboarding document². Since TrCs are responsible for their Nodes training strategy (as available and in place), they should be aware of relevant resources, services and tools^{3,4} available from the ELIXIR TrP and other Nodes in order to also help their Node members be familiar with existing sources available; the core tools TrCs must be familiar with are covered in a document called the critical components of the TrP^{3,4}. In order to make sure onboarding has been successfully completed, evaluation steps are also required. We have, therefore, put together a non-exhaustive TrC onboarding checklist⁵ that addresses all the necessary onboarding steps (along with relevant resources) to support self-assessment and verification of onboarding progress.

Recognition Strategies to Support TrC Engagement

Recognition of TrCs is and must continue to be actively supported by ELIXIR and is essential for sustaining engagement and long-term commitment to the role. Clear and visible recognition mechanisms encourage participation, acknowledge contributions, and help both new and existing TrCs navigate ELIXIR's internal infrastructure effectively.

Currently, TrCs and other contributors (involved in TrP related projects) receive recognition through public attribution of their work, such as contributor profiles linked via GitHub and displayed on ELIXIR training resources, lesson templates (e.g. Train-the-Trainer), and web platforms SPLASH and RDMkit, as well as authorship or acknowledgement in ELIXIR publications and training outputs archived in ELIXIR Zotero Library⁶, ELIXIR Zenodo Community⁷, and/or published via F1000Research Gateway of ELIXIR⁸.

While these mechanisms promote transparency, professional visibility, and career-relevant credit while encouraging best practices in open science, additional and complementary recognition approaches could further enhance engagement and long-term sustainability of the TrC role as well as roles within ELIXIR TrP (such as Work Package leads). For example, ELIXIR could introduce a

¹ [ELIXIR Handbook of Operations - V7.1 April 2025](https://elixir-europe.org/sites/default/files/documents/ELIXIR%20Handbook%20of%20Operations%20-%20V7.1%20April%202025.pdf) (PDF), <https://elixir-europe.org/sites/default/files/documents/ELIXIR%20Handbook%20of%20Operations%20-%20V7.1%20April%202025.pdf>

² [Training Platform - Onboarding info](https://docs.google.com/document/d/1qw3SzkpG23rflfE8vE3OpouU5zT18YpcJxMu_jZq5Jc/edit?tab=t.o#heading=h.zdibnuwb2wp4), https://docs.google.com/document/d/1qw3SzkpG23rflfE8vE3OpouU5zT18YpcJxMu_jZq5Jc/edit?tab=t.o#heading=h.zdibnuwb2wp4

³ [D3.5 Overview of the critical components of the TrP network and relevant resources for TrCs and TrP Node members](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17258955), also available on Zenodo: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17258955>

⁴ [M3.9 Report Critical Components TrP.docx](https://docs.google.com/document/u/0/d/1CxCMasdtaaTXwLfowe5nyf1_Wq9NnhyY/edit), https://docs.google.com/document/u/0/d/1CxCMasdtaaTXwLfowe5nyf1_Wq9NnhyY/edit also available on Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/records/17258955>

⁵ TrC onboarding checklist [ELIXIR TrC Onboarding Checklist](https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1AdoJoDoe_KV-l2EJsKtPFLKjDWv9NsMCIEH071oiExo/edit?gid=1430278371#gid=1430278371) (suggested by Activity 2 Leads of WP3), https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1AdoJoDoe_KV-l2EJsKtPFLKjDWv9NsMCIEH071oiExo/edit?gid=1430278371#gid=1430278371

⁶ ELIXIR Zotero Library https://www.zotero.org/groups/5870857/elixir_training_platform/library

⁷ ELIXIR Zenodo Community <https://zenodo.org/communities/elixir>

⁸ ELIXIR's F1000Research Gateway <https://f1000research.com/elixir>

lightweight digital recognition framework, such as role-based badges or micro-credentials, awarded for sustained contributions (e.g. coordination, mentoring, curriculum development, or cross-Node collaborations) and displayed on ELIXIR profiles, ORCID, or institutional webpages. A central TrC contribution dashboard aggregating activities across platforms (GitHub, Zenodo, Training Metrics Database) could provide both visibility and evidence of impact, supporting career progression and institutional reporting. Further recognition could include annual TrC highlights or awards, showcased through ELIXIR communication channels, and formal references or acknowledgement letters that TrCs can use in performance reviews or funding applications. Collectively, these approaches can standardise recognition across Nodes, reduce bias in support, and strengthen the value proposition of TrC participation within the ELIXIR ecosystem.

Consistent recognition across ELIXIR Nodes helps address observed variability in the level of support provided by the ELIXIR TrP, strengthening the overall ELIXIR training ecosystem and fostering a shared culture of contribution and acknowledgement. These recognition approaches complement existing ELIXIR mechanisms described in other milestones⁹ and collectively maintain the strategic importance and sustainability of the TrC role.

Evaluation and Follow-Up

The onboarding of a TrC to the ELIXIR and the Node environment shall include structured evaluation of the onboarding process, using the checklist⁵ and follow-up mechanisms for evaluation to ensure successful and smooth integration and role readiness. Since there is no documentation or known mechanisms available, some suggestions can be proposed based also on the Milestone from PeoplePulse CoS WP2 M2.2 ELIXIR Onboarding Protocol.¹⁰

Regular checkpoints could be scheduled throughout the onboarding period to assess progress, clarify expectations, and identify support needs, recognising that these may vary depending on prior experience and role responsibilities. A mentor could be assigned for the first 3–6 months, providing guidance and a dedicated channel for feedback. Feedback loops could include both informal check-ins and formal reviews, allowing the TrC to reflect on their onboarding experience while enabling ELIXIR and the Node to assess the effectiveness of the process. Since different Nodes have different needs of support, the onboarding of the TrC is a process that needs adapted methods of evaluation as well.

Supporting Documents

- [M3.10 Current Practices TrC TrP](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17258995)<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17258995>
- [D3.5 Report Critical Components TrP.docx](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17252853) <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17252853>
- [M3.9 Report Critical Components TrP.docx](https://zenodo.org/records/17258955)<https://zenodo.org/records/17258955>

⁹ M3.11 Training Coordinator (TrC) Terms of Reference [M3.11 TrC Terms of Reference](https://docs.google.com/document/u/o/d/1SwJk_e5EGN8iZtY_cKuTUSIM6gSYBGd2raA-1E5RJy4/edit), https://docs.google.com/document/u/o/d/1SwJk_e5EGN8iZtY_cKuTUSIM6gSYBGd2raA-1E5RJy4/edit

¹⁰ PeoplePulse CoS | WP2 | M2.2 ELIXIR Onboarding Protocol - <https://zenodo.org/records/17202558>

- PeoplePulse CoS | WP2 | M2.2 ELIXIR Onboarding Protocol - <https://zenodo.org/records/17202558>

Dissemination Plans

This document will be published on Zenodo and will be available in Zotero under the Training Platform 2024-2026 work plan library.